

Particle Size Measurement of Silole Nano-clusters by Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy

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Abstract: Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy (FCS) was used to study the nano-clusters of silole molecules formed by aggregation from solutions in acetone-water mixtures. It allowed the determination of the size of clusters in nanometer scale. Aggregate formation was investigated systematically by measuring the cluster sizes made at different silole concentrations and water contents.

1. Introduction

Fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS) is a powerful tool to investigate particles diffusing in solution, and has been widely used in chemistry and biology since its first introduction in early 1970s [1]. Sensitivity to the dye concentration and the diffusion coefficient made it suitable to study the aggregation of molecules in solution. In this work, we investigated the aggregates of silole molecules in solution using FCS. The hexaphenylsilole (HPS) molecule studied consists of a silole center surrounded by six phenyl rings. The fluorescence quantum yield of this molecule in isolation is very low. However, when these molecules form aggregates, the quantum yield increases dramatically. This unique phenomenon of aggregation-induced emission enhancement (AIEE) is due to the hindered rotation of pendant phenyl rings when they form the aggregates, which would work to block the nonradiative decay pathway [2,3]. As water is a poor solvent of silole, acetone/water mixture with higher water content facilitated the cluster formation. The size of the nano-clusters, however, depended more on the concentration of silole molecules in solution than water content of the mixture.

2. Theoretical Background

Principles of FCS and derivation of correlation function to analyze measured time traces are well established [4]. As the signal is temporal fluctuations of fluorescence from dyes in the focal volume defined by excitation beam and confocal geometry, autocorrelation analysis can be used to extract useful information from the fluctuations. For m diffusing species, autocorrelation function can be written as

$$G(\tau) = \sum_i^m \frac{Q_i^2 \bar{N}_i}{\left(\sum_j^m Q_j \bar{N}_j \right)^2} \left(\frac{1}{1 - 4D_i \tau / r_0^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{1 - 4D_i \tau / z_0^2} \right)$$

Here, the confocal detection volume has three-dimensional Gaussian shape with lateral and longitudinal sizes r_0 and z_0 , respectively. D is diffusion coefficient of dye molecule and Q represents the brightness of single aggregate. N is the average number of aggregates inside the focal volume. In this work, the origin of the fluctuations is only from the Brownian diffusion of silole in and out of the focal volume. The size of the silole nano-clusters can be calculated from the measured diffusion coefficient using Einstein-Stokes relation.

3. Result & discussion

Acetone-water mixtures of various compositions were used to make 100 nM and 1 μ M silole solutions. FCS setup consisted of microscope objective with NA=1.2 and the 400 nm-laser beam to excite the molecules. Fluorescence signal detected by avalanche photodiode was processed by software to yield the correlation function. As Brownian motion is responsible for the observed autocorrelation function, the lag time where the correlation amplitude drop down to the half of its original value at $\tau=0$ corresponds to the diffusion time, an average resident time of particles in confocal detection volume, As this diffusion time is inversely proportional to the diffusion coefficient and the diffusion coefficient is again inversely proportional to the particle size, we could obtain the size of the nano-clusters in solution.

For 100 nM-silole solution, nano-clusters are found dominantly in solutions with high water content as expected, with the cluster size 20 ~ 70 nm. It was also true for 1 μ M-silole solution except the size of the nano-clusters was much bigger (100 nm ~ 1000 nm) than that from 100 nM-silole solution. Thus we deduced that the size of the nano-clusters is determined by silole concentration but not by the solvent composition, while the ratio of water to acetone determines whether the clusters are formed or not.

4. References

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